

Paper 6

EXPLORING THE AVENUES OF DEVELOPING THE INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE GROWTH OF INSTITUTE TOWARDS QUALITY EDUCATION

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Abstract

Good infrastructure facilities is crucial for rapid growth and to maintain the quality standard in educational institute. Education institutes are substantially lagging behind. Equal importance has to be given to infrastructure including classroom, library, sports and games, yoga and cultural activities. Academic institutes need to invest in various divisions of infrastructure which should provide for the growth of young students graduating at the university level education which leads to the overall development of different departments of the university. The study then tries to identify key challenges to infrastructure development and discusses following the various criteria's and possible ways in which these challenges can be addressed. This in turn helps the institute or university to increase its score under NAAC evaluation system.

Keywords: Infrastructure, Growth and Quality Standard.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education system in India should be accorded an “infrastructure” status to attract investments in regions where access to higher educational means is limited. Adequate infrastructure facilities are key for effective and efficient conduct of the educational programmes. The growth of the infrastructure thus has to keep pace with the academic developments in the institution.

With the mode of teaching changing, faculty roles will change from just information sharing to problem solving. This could facilitate a customised learning experience, utilising means such as advanced tablets, cloud technologies and new devices, ensuring easier scalability.

Industry should be encouraged to participate in curriculum framing, teaching and provision of internships and placements utilising funds available through CSR to create Centres of Excellence, Innovation Hubs as well as encouraging endowments for faculty positions, capacity development, and upkeep of infrastructure.

The other supportive facilities on the campus are developed to contribute to the effective ambience for curricular, extra-curricular and administrative activities.

OBJECTIVES

- To provide the best service to the graduates in higher education institutions.
- To prepare students for a more global and competitive working pattern.

DISCUSSION

- **CLASSROOMS**

Based on the nature of subject the classroom should have infrastructure required –LCD Projector, Wi-Fi connection the classes have to be rotated as per the requirements. preparing timetable all the department must coordinate to avoid back to back classes and overlapping.

During university/ competitive exams examination control room must be allotted for systematic and proper procedure to be followed to avoid mistakes and confusion.

Auditorium can be used for guest lecture to interact with the graduates to pass on the knowledge from industry to the budding candidates

- **COMPUTER LAB**

Ratio required is 2:1 (Number of students: Number of computer) has to be maintained for better learning and understanding of the subject and also opportunity for the graduates to practice and get the skills required.

Proper periodic maintenance of systems in computer lab to keep the systems at its best

proper UPS battery backup must be provided for better system maintenance. Use the latest or upgraded software's available in the market. The hardware components should be as per as the latest software requirements. Total security software must be provided to ensure the data security. Increase the speed of the internet to save time and use the required software effectively.

Software available

- Linux/ Fedora/ Mint

- Gimp
- Gedit
- Open Office
- MySql
- Apache
- Bluefish
- Audacity

• **CULTURAL AND SPORTS**

Intercollegiate cultural events should be encouraged. Cultural events must be done in odd semester and sports events must be done in even semester National level fest should be encouraged in all the streams to show the talent and overall development of a graduate. Students must be encouraged and motivated to visit other colleges and perform to get the awards which has to be recorded and documented and also helps in achieving the right weight age during the NAAC assessment.

Various events like Freshers Day, Talents Day, Traditional day and Farewell Day must be done.

Various cultural programs must be arranged during occasions like Independence day, Karnataka Rajyotsava, Onam.

Sports and cultural events outside participation among students must be encouraged.

Student counselling committee must be done. Various forums like Fine art, Sports, IT.

Project exhibition such as marketing, economic and picture perfect exhibition must be done.

Yoga must be considered as part of curriculum and should be practiced regularly.

Gym facility should be provided.

- Cultural and sports events

Cricket	Dance - solo and group
Football	Singing
Athletics	Talent hunt - musical Instruments
Chess and carom	Mine
Volleyball	Skit - current topics in business and social cause
Throw ball - girls	Offstage events - (painting, cooking without fire, pencil sketch)
Kabaddi	

- **LIBRARY**

Library has to be digitalized where the issue, return and availability of the books can be easily monitored. 1 or 2 latest edition books has to be ordered and more copies can be generated for students and faculties. Increase the return date duration of books issued for students to have better use of the material available. Book bank facility must be provided by nominal charges.

Create newspaper and magazine section separately for students to keep themselves updates with the current happenings and the business decisions taken by corporate.

Use of digital library must be encouraged among students with the membership available

ISSN journals should be made available for the encouragement of faculty and student collaborative research work. Extending library hours during study holiday and examination. Proper automated records of people arriving and leaving the library should be maintained. Library slot has to be provided for students to refer for all purposes to ensure students visit library regularly. Staff and student registers are maintained.

Library documents available

- Proof of Library automation as integrated Library System (SAAS)
- NDL- National Digital Library and Inflibnet facility are available.
- SWAYAM is installed and functional for students to listen to talks and acquire the required knowledge from other sources available
- E- Content facility is provided.

MAINTENANCE

Dustbin must be provided in corridor of every floor. To keep the campus clean and hygiene

Tree plantation drives must be conducted in every sem. Periodic painting and white washing of building must be done for the appearance to maintain a better impression and it contributes to the admission for each course.

Annual maintenance for critical equipments to avoid breakdown and stoppage Backup generator of 150 KV in case of disturbance in regular power supply from MESCOM should be ready. Maintenance of stock registers for office, computer lab, library and classrooms and carry out periodic audit. Budget allocation for office, computer lab, library and classrooms.

Sufficient seating arrangements must be provided in the cafeteria for staff and students

Systematic parking slots can be done for staff and students separately. Rest room should be provided with proper first aid kit. Fire Extinguisher cylinder should be installed in every floor

which can be used in case of emergency. Separate boys and girls hostel are available with all the facilities required for students coming from other places to take the admission for the course.

CONCLUSION

We look at availability of facilities such as proper physical infrastructure, computer labs, and library facilities. It is heartening to see that majority of the learning resources and infrastructure is being utilized by graduates and faculties for their quality overall development that has impact on graduates and institute. It is in this context further challenge still remains to provide a conducive learning environment to all graduates to close the gap which is present between the industry needs and the education provided in higher education

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